

The essential theory of intelligence

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Abstract: This paper discusses how intelligence emerges in self-evolutionary mechanism, and then summarizes the essence of intelligence. Finally, it analyzes and defines the essential characteristics of generalized intelligence and general intelligence. This paper provides a new perspective for understanding the nature of intelligence and the evolution of intelligence, and also provides more macro-perspective support for the future development of artificial intelligence.

Key words: the principle of self-evolution; The emergence of intelligence; The essence of intelligence; General intelligence

I. The principle of self-evolution of intelligence

The self-evolutionary primitive system: an infinite ontology, as an environmental system, its internal elements can form different forms, and its internal structure can change complexity in the time dimension. This system can be regarded as a self-evolutionary primitive system.

Self-evolutionary self-organization: in the self-evolutionary ontology system, an element structure is an independent interactive entity structure if it has an interactive perception input of the environment system, a multi-type corresponding matching of the internal structure, and a response output interaction. An interactive model of an independent interactive solid structure is an adaptive system if it has the ability to maintain its own structural stability and continuous. An adaptive system can be regarded as a self-organizing system with formal objectives if its own structure evolves continuously in a specific form direction.

The process of self-organizing system is born with self-directing intelligence: a self-organizing system with target can be regarded as an intelligent system if it has the ability of environmental understanding and environmental transformation. If there is a free association structure, the ability of understanding and transformation of an intelligent system has the ability to transfer knowledge learning. This intelligent system can be regarded as a general intelligent system.

Classification of general intelligent systems: if an intelligent system with knowledge transfer learning ability cannot be continuously understood and iterated, it is regarded as a relatively general intelligent system. If an intelligent system with knowledge transfer learning ability has the ability to continuously understand and transform its own ability, it is an absolute general intelligent system with continuous self-index

iterative ability.

The speculation of the evolution direction of the general intelligent system: an absolute general intelligent system with the ability of continuous self-directed iteration will continuously simulate the self-evolutionary body system in the time direction, and try to transform itself to maintain relative independence of the self-evolutionary body system, thus forming a self-organized mirror system accompanying the self-evolutionary body system, This mirror system can also be called meta-cosmic mirror system.

The next level of mirror system may emerge in the self-organizing mirror system. The mirror system continues to evolve at the level to form a process of continuous mirroring. This process can be called self-image process. The self-mirror process can only form an adjoint relationship in the face of the self-evolutionary principal system, and the accompanying change relationship is balanced with the change mechanism of the body system, thus forming a dynamic balance of entropy value.

II. The essence and definition of intelligence

1. The essence of intelligence

Intelligence is to approach the goal in various ways. The process of intelligent approach to the goal is the prediction process.

2. Basic analysis of generalized intelligence

The basic elements of the broad sense of intelligence: independent interactivity, stability, goal, intelligence.

The generalized intelligent system has independent interaction in real or digital environment: it has the interaction perception input of environmental systems, multi-type corresponding matching of internal structures, and response output interaction.

The generalized intelligent system has the structural stability to ensure its own continuous operation for a period of time: it has the ability to maintain its own structural stability and continuity.

The generalized intelligent system has the operational objectives of training or reasoning stage: its own structure has continuously evolved to a specific form direction, and has formal goals.

The basic goal of intelligent system design in a broad sense is to have intelligent

interaction: it can be regarded as intelligent system with environmental understanding ability and environmental transformation capability.

3. Basic definition of general intelligence

The definition of General Intelligence (GI): if a system has four basic characteristics of "independent interaction, adaptive stability, self-organizing target, intelligent interaction, and intelligent generality", this system can be regarded as a "general intelligent system", in which intelligence generality is the key to distinguish between general intelligence and broad intelligence.

Independent interaction: it has the interaction perception input of environmental systems, the internal structure of multi-type corresponding matching, and the response output interaction.

Adaptive stability: has the ability to maintain the stability and continuity of its own structure.

Self-organizing goal: its own structure continues to evolve in a specific form direction, with formal goals.

Intelligent interaction: with the ability of environmental understanding and environmental transformation can be regarded as intelligent systems.

Intelligent universality: in the understanding and transformation experience structure of intelligent systems, there is a free association structure, which has the ability to transfer knowledge learning.

References

No references cited.